

Minutes of the 48th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Tuesday 24th January 2012
(This document was finalised on 5th April 2012)

Present:

Mr Graeme Anderson³
Dr Bogdan Antonescu⁶ (BA)
Mr Owen Cox³ (OC)
Mr Les Dean^{1,4} (LD)
Dr Jon Eastment^{4,5} (JDE)
Mr Mike Edwards³
Dr Catherine Gaffard³ (CG)
Dr David Hooper^{4,5} (DAH) Secretary
Mr Dan Housley⁶ (DJH)
Dr Dirk Klugmann³ (DK)
Dr Chris Lee⁶ (CFL)
Dr Graham Parton^{2,5} (GAP)
Dr Jeremy Price³ (JP)
Prof Geraint Vaughan⁶ (GV) Chair

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²British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

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⁴NERC MST Radar Facility

⁵Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁶University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BL(WP) Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
DIAMET DIAbatic influences on Mesoscale structures in ExTropical storms
EUCOS EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FAAM Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
FGAM Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements
GPS Global Positioning System
IOP Intensive Observation Period
LCBR Laser Cloud Base Recorder
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
NLC Noctilucent Cloud
PC Personal Computer
PV Potential Vorticity
TROSIAD TROopause folding, Stratospheric Intrusions And Deep convection
UM Unified Model
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 47th meeting were accepted without corrections.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.4.1 DK to set up a working group for developing quality control algorithms for wind-profiling radars.

ONGOING

There has been some activity on this item although, so far, with a limited outcome.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik LCBRs on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he had obtained some sample files from the Met Office. Once the metadata issues have been finalised, files will start to be uploaded to the BADC. OC reported that he had recently chaired a working group, which was looking at the encoding of ceilometer data into BUFR and netCDF files.

ACTION ITEM 46.6.1 DK to set up a working group for those with expertise in lidar operations.

DISCONTINUED

DK reported that the group will initially be an informal one and so it no longer needs to have an action item associated with it. At present the level of activity on lidars within the Met Office is quite low as DK has recently lost a number of people from his team. Nevertheless, he is looking to recruit 3 new members of staff.

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not had time to address the two actions above, but that he would prioritise them after the MST13 Workshop in March 2012. GV re-emphasised the need to assign them the highest possible priority.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.1 DAH and GAP to remove from public view, as soon as possible, those cloud base altitude files which have incorrect time stamps.

COMPLETED

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

A report on the above two items is given in section 3c.

ACTION ITEM 47.5.1 GAP to ensure that the BADC archive Met Office lightning data to cover the TROSIAD campaign period.

ONGOING

Some data are already available and BA has been analysing them in the context of the TROSIAD project. GAP reported that the BADC is working with the Met Office to define a netCDF file which can be used to store more than just the number of lightning strikes. Data will not appear on the BADC until this is finalised.

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) Electricity, including NERC's Voltage Optimisation scheme

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units indicated that brief electricity supply disruptions (i.e. with durations of no more than 1 s) occurred on 1st August and 1st September 2011. Longer disruptions are rare. Nevertheless, two (one of 10 s and the second of 20 s) occurred on 21st December 2011 and a third (of 12 s) occurred on the following day. The UPS units can continue to power equipment for at least 20 minutes in the event of a complete loss of mains electricity.

NERC has installed equipment for monitoring electricity usage at all of their sites. This has allowed them to estimate the effects of installing voltage optimisation equipment for the purposes of reducing energy consumption - see minutes of the 47th meeting for further details. Estimated savings of between 5% and 10% have been achieved as a result of installing voltage optimisation equipment at some NERC sites. However, there has been no apparent change at the MST radar site. This is unsurprising since all of the heavy loads are powered through UPS units. The efficiency of the latter is unaffected by changes in the input voltage.

For apparently-unconnected reasons, the typical non-winter daily electricity consumption at the radar site has reduced from 242 kWh in 2010 to 194 kWh in 2011, i.e. by almost 20%. Electricity is used for heating during the winter months and so the values tend to be considerably-higher (sometimes in excess of 270 kWh) and highly-variable over time scales of several days (they are virtually constant during summer months). DAH attributes the non-winter change to the lower power requirements of the new MST radar beam steering components. These were installed by ATRAD during March 2011.

The NERC monitoring data have revealed occasional step changes in daily electricity consumption. These are consistent with one of the five MST radar transmitters either going off-line or being restarted. For example, the value increased from 171 kWh on 23rd May 2011 to 195 kWh two days later. LD had restarted one of the transmitters, TX1, at around 10:00 UT on 24th May. The impact of a blown choke, i.e. the cause of the transmitter failure in this case, is not immediately-apparent from the diagnostic information available through the front panel displays. However, the drop in transmit power levels for an entire sector of the antenna array is clearly visible from the monitoring software for the new beam steering components. This was spotted by a member of ATRAD staff, who happened to be making remote checks on the equipment. It was initially thought that the transmitter had been out of action for only a few days. However, the daily electricity consumption data suggest that it had been off-line since 27th April 2011, when the value had dropped from 191 to 169 kWh. LD now routinely inspects the monitoring information from the new beam steering equipment. Consequently there have been no further occasions when a failed transmitter goes unnoticed for prolonged periods. An analysis of the electricity consumption data for 2010, i.e. for the period before the new monitoring information was available, suggests that the radar was running on no more than 4 transmitters between 4th July and 27th August 2010. Within this period, only 3 transmitters appear to have been in operation between 21st July

and 3rd August 2010.

CFL pointed out that the radar's beam pattern would be significantly altered by one or more of the transmitters being out of action. This is likely to affect the measured spectral widths and therefore estimates of turbulence intensity. DAH recognised that this was probably the case. However, he observed that the loss of a single transmitter did not appear to have a significant impact on the wind-profile data. Periods when a transmitter is known to have been out of action are recorded in the instrument event log - http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3b) Telecommunications

The Draytek broadband modem, which was installed on 19th June 2011, has operated faultlessly for the past six months. Nevertheless, there have been 2 occasions (between 09:00 and 17:30 UT on 21st July 2011, and between 15:20 UT on 5th January 2012 and 09:30 UT the following day) when the internet connection was unavailable. These appear to have been the result of external line problems. On a third occasion (between 22:45 UT on 13th October 2011 and 12:00 UT on the following day) the loss of connection appears to have been the result of an internal line problem. It was resolved by some generic cable wiggling.

DAH is proposing to switch to a new broadband package, albeit with the same internet service provider, for both the NERC and Manchester lines. Eclipse's "*Business Bronze*" package has a 50 GByte peak-time usage allowance for half of the cost of the current unlimited package. Typical monthly usage is just a few GByte on the NERC line (presumably this implies downloads only as approximately 10 GByte of data are transferred back to RAL each month) and has only once exceeded 10 GByte on the Manchester line. DAH is also proposing to make use of Eclipse's "*TalkMore Business*" package, which gives 1000 free minutes of telephone calls per month to 01, 02 and 03 numbers. This will save approximately 40 a quarter on the "fax line", which is used solely for dial-up connections to the Frongoch data logger. Even greater savings will be made on the phone line.

3c) Data management

In connection with action item 47.3.1, the laser ceilometer cloud base files for the period 2nd November 2010 - 10th September 2011 have been removed from public view on the BADC. The underlying problem is the slow drift of the instrument's internal clock - see minutes of the 46th meeting for further details. At present DAH hard-codes time corrections into the software which creates NASA-Ames data files from the original data logs. However, this requires a manual inspection of the log files and a change in the software every time the accumulated slippage changes by 1 s. Consequently DAH wants to delay recreating the files affected by action item 47.3.1 until he has written an automatic correction algorithm. In the meantime, the hidden files can be made available upon request.

The MST radar ST-mode data files for the period 6th February 2007 - 8th April 2008 have also been removed from public view on the BADC. These files are affected by a range gating error, which is described at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/announce_20080416.html. Given that updating the signal processing software, i.e. action item 47.2.1, is now his DAH's top priority, he does not plan to issue corrections for the affected (i.e. version 3.2) files. Instead he will concentrate on reprocessing the entire observation archive, with the correction included, using the next version (i.e. 3.3) of the software, i.e. action item 47.2.2. Once again, the hidden files can be made available upon request.

Over the past six months there have been a number of issues with BADC computers. These have led to some of the MSTRF daily products files being initially incomplete or absent. The most significant of these issues was the hacking of the BADC's web services on 13th September 2011. However, relatively minor technical problems on 16th October 2011, 8th November, 21st December, and 5th and 16th January 2012 have also had consequences. Although DAH thinks that he has (re)generated all of the necessary files, users should let him know if they find any data gaps.

3d) Miscellaneous

A swarm of Honey Bees visited the radar site on 14th July 2011. However, unlike in previous years, they do not appear to have stayed for very long.

The main security camera was repaired on 9th August 2011. It had been encountering problems with the steering mechanism. This was resolved by removing a build-up of dead flies from the housing.

On 6th October 2011, Radio 4's "Material World" science programme featured a short interview with DAH. It can be heard through the following link - <http://www.bbc.co.uk/iplayer/console/b015crkj> - just after 22 minutes into the broadcast. The interview arose from DAH's contact with John Rowlands, an amateur noctilucent cloud (NLC) spotter, who had featured in the programme's "So You Want to Be a Scientist" competition in 2010. John had been mentored by Prof Nick Mitchell (University of Bath) in a project looking at the relationship between NLC occurrence and mesopause temperatures. DAH had proposed that the project could be extended to consider Mesosphere Summer Echos (MSEs) observed by the MST radar. The work has started to yield some interesting results and will be presented as a poster at the MST13 workshop in March 2012.

Vince Lean, from the Met Office, visited the radar site on 28th November 2011. He was making an assessment of works necessary for the installation one of the Met Office's Jenoptik laser ceilometers. OC confirmed that the Met Office still aim to go ahead with this deployment.

A NERC Radar Forum was held in Cambridge on 5th January 2012. DAH, JDE and GV had attended together with representatives of other atmospheric/ionospheric radar facilities/networks, including from the Met Office. Although there had been concerns that the meeting would be dominated by budgetary issues, the focus had in fact been on technical and scientific concerns of common interest. GV pointed out that there would be a NERC thematic programme on Space Weather within the next few years. This will be of particular relevance for the ionospheric radars, for which science funding has recently moved from the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) to NERC.

The wooden sheds within the middle of the MST radar antenna array, which house the primary power splitters, are due to be replaced during March/April 2012. This will require the radar to be powered down for up to 5 full working days, i.e. between 9 am and 5 pm. The existing huts are over 20 years old and are in a very poor state of repair.

DAH reported that Helen Clark had highlighted the following paper, which might be of interest to attendees of the meeting: Forrest M. Mims III, Lin Hartung Chambers, and David R. Brooks, 2011, Measuring total column water vapor by pointing an infrared thermometer at the sky, *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 92, 13111320. It is an open access publication and can be freely downloaded from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/2011BAMS3215.1>.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There have been no issues with this set of instruments during the past 6 months.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

There have been 3 occasions when the data logger failed to capture readings: between 08:00 UT on 13th October 2011 and 18:00 UT on the 15th, between 04:45 and 13:00 UT on 16th October 2011, and between 08:34 UT on 3rd January 2012 and 12:00 on the 5th. Sporadic readings captured during these

periods are of dubious validity. In the first case, the onset of the problem coincided with an internet connection issue - see section 3c. It is not clear whether or not the two are related. In the third case, the onset of the problem coincided with unusually high wind speeds, i.e. 15 minute mean values in excess of 15 m s^{-1} . However, LD could not see any signs of damage to the instruments when he subsequently visited Frongoch. The problem was resolved without any intervention being taken.

GV pointed out that files containing data of dubious quality could cause problems for anyone analysing them without knowing about this issue. Consequently such files should be removed from public view.

ACTION ITEM 48.4.1 DAH and GAP to remove from public view on the BADC those surface wind files which are known to contain data of dubious quality.

NEW

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

On 20th August 2011, this instrument failed to detect four mild rain events (i.e. with rates 1 mm hour^{-1}) which were seen by the tipping bucket rain gauge: at around 00:30, 04:00, 09:00, and 14:00 UT. However, it managed to detect the final rain event at around 23:00 UT. There have been no subsequent discrepancies between the two sets of measurements. Consequently it is probably that the rain in question was falling too lightly to generate a measurable piezo-electric signal on the WXT510.

JP expressed an interest in the WXT510's sonic anemometer wind data. He would like to study cold pool formation and thought that the Capel Dewi valley might be a suitable location. However, he wasn't sure if the presence of trees and hedgerows might be an issue. DAH pointed out that the valley had been covered by Google Streetview a few summers ago. JP could use this to get a better idea of both terrain and vegetation. CFL pointed out that much of the surrounding land was owned by Aberystwyth University. Consequently it may be possible to gain permission to deploy additional instruments nearby.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There have been no issues with this instrument during the past six months.

4e) Sky-camera

DAH supervised a work experience student at RAL during the week of 11th - 15th July 2011. This was the 5th student to have worked on the project of recording the beginning and end date-times of interesting atmospheric phenomena visible in the sky-camera images. The event log now spans almost the first year of operation, i.e. 25th April 2007 - 1st April 2008.

4f) MST Radar

The Met Office model-comparison statistics indicate good data quality over the past six months. The values of the alternative EUCOS "quality" parameter (i.e. the root mean square difference between measured and model winds - see minutes of the 47th meeting for further details) are 3.8, 3.6, 3.9, 5.1, 4.3 and 4.4 m s^{-1} for June - November 2011. Except for September value of 5.1 m s^{-1} , these easily exceeded the EUCOS target of a maximum value of 5.0 m s^{-1} . "Availability" values were all in excess of 97% (the target is a minimum of 95%) and "timeliness" values were all in excess of 96% (minimum of 90%).

There have been only two unexpected outages of the radar during the past six months. The first, between 18:30 UT on 16th July 2011 and 00:30 UT the following morning, was the result of the new beam steering controller failing to change the beam pointing direction. Clearly-erroneous wind-profile data were flagged as being reliable for the earlier part of this period, i.e. 18:30 - 22:50 UT. The radar stopped working altogether thereafter. Ironically the problem was a result of an ATRAD engineer remotely investigating a previous beam steering problem. The second incident, between 01:16 and 11:00

UT on 16th November 2011, was also caused by an ATRAD engineer remotely investigating a problem - this time with the error-logging system. ATRAD have now been instructed to only carry out software changes with prior permission from DAH.

In recent years, internal interference has been one of the most common problems affecting the radar. However, since the last Experimenters' meeting, it has occurred on only 4 occasions - on 5th, 7th, 8th, and 9th July 2011 - and hasn't been seen since. Nevertheless, there have been frequent problems with one of the transmitters, TX1, going off-line after blowing its choke or its fuse: on 12th July 2011, on several occasions between 16th July and 11th August, on 22nd, 26th, and 27th September, on 30th October, on 15th and 29th November 2011, and on 19th and 21st January 2012. Refer also to details given in section 3a. In each case, there was a significant elevation of the noise floor when the transmitter went down. This was most-apparent in the m-mode data plots but also lead to reductions in the useful wind coverage for st-mode observations. The quality of the wind-profile data should not have been otherwise significantly affected. Although the problem was quickly identified in all cases, it could take several days before LD was able to visit the site and to resolve the problem. DAH thanked LD for making several unscheduled visits to the site, e.g. on Saturday 21st January 2012, which has helped to limit transmitter down time.

This symptom of a raised noise floor when a transmitter is down has only been seen since the new beam steering components were installed. The reason remains unknown, despite LD having undertaken several special tests. For example, he disconnected TX1 from the antenna array at around 11:30 UT on 4th November 2011. This caused an increase in the noise level. However, the level dropped back down to normal when he reconnected TX1's output but disconnected the receiver input from the corresponding sector of the antenna array. He also carried out tests on 1st, 8th, 11th and 15th November 2011. Efforts to resolve the issue are ongoing.

GV asked whether it was possible to substitute the spare transmitter. However, LD pointed out that it had been used as a source of spare parts for the other transmitters over the years. Consequently it would require a lot of attention in order to bring it back to working order. He did not have sufficient time to do this with just 10 hours per week being devoted to the facility. JDE thought that RAL staff rates would make this prohibitively expensive as an in-house job. Nevertheless, it might be possible to find an external contractor who was able to take on the job. GV emphasised the need for a backup in case one of the transmitters suffered from a catastrophic failure.

ACTION ITEM 48.4.1 DAH and JDE to investigate the opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order.

NEW

The radar was powered down between 11:00 and 13:00 UT on 14th July 2011 to allow weed spraying to be carried out within the antenna array. LD pointed out that some small shrubs were taking root in the fringes of the array. These have proved to be resistant to weed spraying.

One of the transmitters was powered down for maintenance for much of the day on 22nd November 2011. A second one was powered down between 13:00 and 15:30 UT whilst Aberystwyth University MSc students to carried out a surveying practical in one of the outer sectors of the antenna array. The radar was stopped between 10:30 and 11:15 UT on 10th January 2012 to allow LD to change one of the phasing units (for quad 62). The beam steering controller had been consistently showing unusual readings for this unit. LD had not wanted to make changes during the DIAMET/TROSIAD campaign period.

On 16th August 2011 DAH discovered that the legacy (non-operational) "txstatus" program, which is used to remotely interrogate the transmitters, was no longer working. It turns out that the RS-232 in-

terface cables had been disconnected, although it is not known when this occurred. It could have been when electrical testing was carried out on 1st December 2010 or it could have been at the time of the radar renovation in March 2011.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - GV

The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) was moved to Capel Dewi, from Cardington, during August 2011 so that it could support the DIAMET/TROSIAD campaign. Emily Norton had set up a quick-look plotting facility on the DIAMET website in time for this. The instrument will return to Cardington for most of 2012. CG reported that the Met Office hopes to assimilate the wind-profile data if the quality looks good enough. Consequently they will be monitoring the data closely. The data for the campaign period had been sent to the Met Office but were not assimilated.

The BLWP's processing PC suffered from a catastrophic failure at 16:00 on Friday 23rd December 2011. This has now been replaced with a laptop. DAH warned that laptops are not designed to dissipate heat quickly enough to allow intensive processing over prolonged periods. GV clarified that the processing load was quite low and that the new arrangement appeared to be working well.

5b) University of Manchester instruments - GV

The fixed lidar was used during the TROSIAD campaign, mostly for measuring ozone rather than water vapour. The Elight lidar was run for much of the period, but eventually developed a problem. It has recently been moved to RAL, where it will be operated in support of the Clearflo campaign. It appears to have a problem with the laser cooling unit. Hugo Ricketts, who should have been at the current Experimenters' meeting, was instead at RAL in an attempt to fix it. Moreover, there had been a blow-out of one of the tyres en route between Aberystwyth and RAL. The repair man thought that the tyre had degraded from the combination of remaining static for long periods and of repeated fluctuations between wet and dry conditions. GV pointed out that the BLWP had received new tyres (and wheels) as part of its recent refurbishment. It had been returned to Degreane between May and August 2011. It has been fitted with new antenna panels and cables.

During the 3 months of the TROSIAD campaign, 45 radiosondes were launched from the radar site. Although the mobile antenna system had previously proved to be inadequate for tracking radiosondes from the site, good results had been obtained with the fixed mushroom antenna. Data were generally available for altitudes up to 20 km. However, owing to the blocking effects of the valley sides, data were only available up to approximately 8 km for the few occasions when the radiosonde travelled predominantly towards the north or the south. The system now has the latest model of Vaisala digital receiver, i.e. the same type as is used at Cardington. A small hack was necessary in order to integrate it with the existing components. DJH pointed out that it was now possible to process the raw radiosonde data to produce "fledt" files. These store relative humidities as floating point numbers and so avoid the rounding errors associated with "edt" files.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

DAH read out a report from Jon Jones, who was not at the meeting.

There is still a timing issue with the GPS receiver at the radar site. All files are coming in an hour late. Therefore although the data archive is complete, the files are not being processed by the operational system.

The Met Office are currently processing hourly data from around 230 stations across Europe. The estimates of integrated water vapour, from the atmospheric delays, are operationally assimilated into the NAE and UK4 models. Jon is working on a processing system to allow assimilation from a worldwide

network into the Met Office's global model. This is showing a significant positive impact. Since GPS receivers are widespread, they can extend humidity measurements to previously data-sparse regions. Consequently Jon is constantly looking for new overseas partners. He is also working on a sub-hourly processing system to deliver data to the Met Office UKV 1.5km model.

The Met Office have begun to work with NOAA (the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) on a Space Weather service. The total electron content (TEC) of the upper atmosphere gives rise to an ionospheric delay of GPS signals. Normally this is computed as a way of improving positioning accuracy. It can be used to estimate the ionospheric state instead.

5d) Lightning detector - DAH

A lightning detector has been operated at the radar site, on behalf of the German company Nowcast, for just over a year. Lightning information for Europe is derived from a network rather than from individual instruments. It had been hoped that information would be of use for the DIAMET/TROSIAD campaign. However, the fact that only the latest data can be seen made this a resource of limited use.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) DIAbatic influences on Mesoscale structures in ExTropical storms (DIAMET) - GV

The DIAMET campaign took place during the autumn of 2011. A total of 9 intensive observation periods (IOPs) focused on frontal passages and severe winds. The first phase of the campaign, during September 2011, provided favourable conditions. The remnants of Hurricane Katia were responsible for severe surface winds across Scotland on 11th and 12th September, i.e. just before the start of the campaign. There were 3 flights during the September period.

On 16th September 2011, a cloud band ahead of an innocuous-looking occluded front intensified. The main question concerns whether the release of latent heat had an affect on the larger scale. The FAAM aircraft initially flew at high levels and deployed dropsondes. It then descended through the cloud band, where temperatures of between 0 and -10°C gave rise to multi-phase water conditions. High ozone concentrations (200 parts per billion by volume) were seen in association with the Potential Vorticity (PV) anomaly. The time series of radiosonde profiles shows the dry stratospheric air within the tropopause fold and the humid air feeding into the cloud band. The wind shear within the fold shows up clearly in the MST radar observations and the heavy convective rainfall shows up in the surface meteorological observations.

A second IOP, on 20th September 2011, was characterised by a long, trailing cold front. A wave depression, which is difficult to forecast, can kick off anywhere along the front. The system as a whole remained stationary for the entire day, so rainfall accumulations were large. The rain radar images show a succession of waves and banding near the front. The model was unable to represent the small scale structures and so there was poor agreement between the 4 hour forecast and the observations. The FAAM aircraft performed high level transects. These showed pulses of dry air. The Chilbolton radar gave very interesting data for this day.

The merging of two fronts gave rise to an extremely sharp cold front, which passed over on 28th and 29th November 2011. The surface meteorological observations from the MST radar site show a sharp drop in temperature, a pulse of heavy rain, and a change in low-level wind direction. The wind speed did not respond so rapidly. The FGAM BLWP, which was at the radar site, observed the change in wind direction at progressively later times with increasing altitude. The MST radar observations clearly indicate the shear layer along the lower edge of the jet. However, this was still at an altitude of 4 km when the surface front passed over the site. This leads GV to think that there was more than one front present. The limited area European model forecast for this event was very accurate. The more-limited area UKV model, at 1.5 km resolution, also did a reasonable job of representing the rain radar features.

Towards the end of the campaign, on 8th December 2011, the FAAM aircraft made dropsonde observations of a putative sting jet over Scotland. This was associated with Windstorm Friedhelm, which brought hurricane-force winds over a large part of Scotland. Consequently this flight attracted considerable media attention. The final flight, to observe a warm front, was made on 12th December 2011.

6b) Tropopause folding, Stratospheric Intrusions And Deep convection (TROSIAD) Case Studies-BA

The aim of TROSIAD was to study the effect of tropopause folds on convective activity. Forty five radiosondes were launched from the MST radar site during 5 IOPs.

One IOP lasted from 10 UT on 24th November 2011 until 10 UT the following day. The location of the tropopause fold is clearly defined by dry air in satellite images of water vapour. Nimrod rainfall radar data indicate deep convective activity developing on the eastern side of the PV anomaly. Radiosondes were launched every 2 or 3 hours from the MST Radar site. The data show a deep region of dry air within the troposphere during much of the first day. However, this had become quite shallow by 22 UT. BA is proposing that the fold under cuts the front in this particular case. The western part of the fold corresponds to a sharp shear layer in the MST radar wind data.

A second IOP, on 29th November 2011, focused on the passage of a cold front. On this occasion, isolated convective cells, rather than deep moist convection, were seen beneath the fold. BA commented on the strange humidity readings from the 18 UT radiosonde. GV thought that the readings could be reliable since they corresponded to a very low tropopause and therefore to a region of very dry stratospheric air.

6c) Cold fronts seen in MST radar data - CFL

During the 29th November 2011 TROSIAD IOP, a short period of heavy rain (i.e. rates 40 mm hour^{-1}) corresponded to the arrival of the surface cold front at the MST radar site. The temperature drop of approximately 5°C (which was also seen at the Whitworth observatory in Manchester) is much larger than the typical value of 2°C for the British Isles. The location of the front at higher altitudes is revealed by sharp changes in the wind vector derived from FGAM BLWP and MST radar observations. CFL has been experimenting with different ways of analysing the wind data in order to automatically detect such features. He found that it was best to initially consider all data, irrespective of whether or not they were flagged as being reliable. The significance of the results must then be evaluated from a visual inspection.

The frontal region showed up in slightly different ways when considering the vertical shear of the horizontal wind vector and the vertical gradient in horizontal wind direction. The latter does not require so much pre-smoothing of the wind data as the former. A running median is used in preference to a running mean as it ignores outlying data points. CFL also looked at the temporal gradients of both the horizontal wind vector and the horizontal wind direction. The front showed up most clearly, as a double structure, in the temporal gradient of direction. However, this also tended to highlight gravity waves - mainly in the lower stratosphere. Consequently he used a combination of the vertical and temporal gradients of direction, which worked well. When these techniques are applied to BLWP data, it is important to use the high-resolution data. The lowest 500 m of the BL are lost when using the 175 m resolution/interval data. GV suggested that better results might be obtained using a more-advanced filter, such as the SavitzkyGolay filter which GAP used in his thesis.

6d) Testing science sensors developed by Reading University- DK

DK presented this work on behalf of Melanie Collins, who had been called away to another meeting at short notice. Reading University have been developing a number of small and inexpensive sensor packages which can be piggy-backed on a standard RS92 radiosonde. A major design criterion is that the supplemental sensors should have a negligible effect on the standard measurements.

The supplemental sensors, together with a data acquisition system, are packaged in a single box. This is securely attached to the main radiosonde housing. The output from the supplemental data acquisition system can be fed directly into the RS92's data transmission module through the existing ozone sensor port.

A solar radiation sensor was calibrated at Reading against a Kipp and Zonen CM11 pyranometer. Flight trials were conducted at Camborne 21st - 24th November 2011. The location of cloud layers could be clearly determined from the measurements, i.e. low and constant values beneath the cloud base, increasing values within the cloud, and larger values above the cloud tops. The latter readings showed fluctuations in time owing to the swing/spin of the housing beneath the balloon. This technique allows multiple cloud layers to be detected. By contrast, remote sensing techniques are typically restricted to detecting the cloud layer which is closest to the instrument. It does not appear that the supplemental sensor had a detrimental effect on the standard meteorological measurements. The additional power requirements were just a few percent of standard usage.

In answer to JP's questions, DK concede that he did not yet know what information the new sensor could yield about the cloud tops that thermodynamic considerations could not. However, it was clear that the standard relative humidity probe tends to smear out cloud top features.

6e) Application of adjoint-based observation sensitivities impact on wind profiler: preliminary results - CG

This presentation was based on a tool developed by Richard Marriott of the Met Office. The adjoint tool allows estimates to be made of the change in forecast error associated with a particular observation - or group of observations. Using this tool is far cheaper than setting up an Observation Simulation Experiment, for which a test instrument is specially set up outside of the regular observation network.

Preliminary results regarding wind-profiler impacts were carried out for the period 22nd - 31st August 2010. The analysis suggests a reduction in forecast error when data from all European wind-profilers are considered. The reduction is most significant when data from the Met Office's South Uist radar are considered alone. At first sight, the results for the Aberystwyth radar suggest a slight increase in error. However, the magnitude of this increase is considerably smaller than the corresponding error bar. DAH pointed out that the test period occurred before the renovation of the radar (March 2011). Model-comparison statistics (see section 4f) suggest that data quality has improved subsequently.

The tool allows the impact to be estimated on a level by level basis. For example, it can be seen that the South Uist profiler has a positive impact at the lower levels but a negative impact at levels above 300 hPa. Consequently data for above 7 km have been blacklisted for assimilation purposes. When data are considered for the whole month, the negative impact appears to be confined to a smaller number of levels.

In the discussion following her presentation, CG pointed out that the root mean square differences between model and observation winds increase for both radiosonde and WP data at lower-stratospheric altitudes. She speculated that this was a result of gravity wave activity, which was not present in the model. However, only the WP data show an increased bias at these levels. CG was disappointed by the apparent lack of impact for the Aberystwyth radar. She would like to repeat the experiment for a post-renovation period. Moreover, she wondered how much the impact of aircraft measurements (i.e. from AMDAR) reduced the apparent need for WP measurements over southern Britain. CG has discovered that WP data are currently being assimilated in the same way as radiosonde data, i.e. only at significant levels rather than at every reported level. As a result, the model misses the fine scale detail. It turns out that only 3 lines of code will need to be changed in order to resolve this situation.

6f - Backscatter forward model - OC

The Met Office has a relatively dense network of 30+ laser ceilometers, which are also known as Laser Cloud Base Recorders (LCBRs). The raw backscatter data have only been collected since the Eyjafjal-lajökull volcanic eruption in Spring 2010. The Met Office now have a processing system in place which both creates plots of the data, which come from both Jenoptik and Vaisala instruments, and stores them in common-format netCDF files.

The observation network is sufficiently dense to allow the data to be used to validate certain variables, e.g. cloud fraction, within the Unified Model (UM). Moreover, the backscatter data could be directly assimilated with the aim of improving the forecast. A “forward operator” will be needed to map the values of UM variables into parameters of more-direct relevance to the instruments.

LCBRs operating in the infra-red are sensitive to scattering from diverse aerosols. The UM has basic capabilities for representing aerosol loading. These are used to calculate visibilities. The aerosols are assumed to be advected through the model by the wind. For simplicity, all aerosols are assumed to be composed of ammonium sulphate, which is hygroscopic. It does not change from crystal to liquid form until the relative humidity exceeds 79%. Above this, the aerosol will increase in size with increasing relative humidity. Although it will shrink again as relative humidity is decreased, it will not revert to its crystal form until the value drops below 38%. It is therefore possible to determine the aerosol size distribution which results from various starting values of aerosol size and relative humidity. Observed and modelled backscatter values can be in good agreement when the resolution of the observations has been degraded to match that of the model. However, the comparisons have been less favourable under conditions of fog. In the longer term, it will be necessary to calibrate the instruments in order to be able to characterise their measurement errors.

7. Any Other Business

LD gave a short report on the potential of using the MST radar as a riometer, i.e. a device for measuring ionospheric absorption. Increases in the level of ionisation will cause increases in the absorption of lower-VHF signals from galactic sources. Diurnal variations in the MST radar spectral noise power have already been attributed to “sky noise”. However, no one has so far looked for day-to-day variations in the absolute values. It is not yet clear who might be interested in the data.

The next Experimenters' meeting, to be held at the Cosener's House, was provisionally scheduled for Thursday 21st June 2012.